

Advantages of the media to students and language learners

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Annotation: The main purpose of this article work is to study the benefits of using various mass media in teaching foreign languages, problems of integration of information and communication technologies into the traditional educational process.

Key words: media, contemporary life, authentic, practice, linguistic media, real life situation, discussion, advance information.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolaning asosiy maqsadi chet tillarini o'qitishda turli ommaviy axborot vositalaridan foydalanishning afzalliklari, an'anaviy o'quv jarayoniga axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarini integratsiyalash muammolarini o'rganishdan iborat.

Kalit so'zlar: ommaviy axborot vositalari, zamonaviy hayot, autentik, amaliyot, lingvistik media, hayotiy vaziyat, muhokama, yangi ma'lumot.

Аннотация: Основной целью работы данной статьи является изучение преимуществ использования различных средств массовой информации при обучении иностранным языкам, проблем интеграции информационно-коммуникационных технологий в традиционный образовательный процесс.

Ключевые слова: СМИ, современная жизнь, аутентичность, практика, языковые медиа, реальная жизненная ситуация, дискуссия, предварительная информация.

We all know that using the media to teach languages a real environment is a double challenge for language teachers. Although the media allow students to be exposed to real language that is used in real life, they themselves also convey pre-planned ideologies. And with help of this research we can explore the importance of the real language of the media in learning and teaching languages, at the same time, improves the understanding of the ideological structure of teachers and students. [4,49]

Researchers use critical linguistics and descriptive analysis to test the ideological representation of the new structure and analyze the grammatical characteristics of the vocabulary to clarify the role of the native language in language learning. It is recommended that teachers provide an analytical framework to help students reflect on their language experience and practice. Teachers can use movies, TV shows, popular music,

news, literature, documentaries, and videos from sources such as YouTube to attract students and produce deeper and more meaningful learning experiences. The use of the media can engage students, help students retain knowledge, stimulate interest in topics, and illustrate the relevance of many concepts. Media can be used in almost any subject to improve the learning effect of classroom learning and homework. You can watch short films and TV clips, written articles, and blog posts to reinforce concepts and spark discussions. Songs and music videos, especially when lyrics are available, can achieve the same effect.

Advantages of the media to students and language learners:

- Popular media (movies, music, YouTube) are media familiar to students, which help attract attention and keep students interested in the theories and concepts discussed.
- Students can see theories and concepts in practice. In a figurative sense, theories and concepts jumped off the screen.
- Students can hone their analytical skills by analyzing the media using the theories and concepts they are studying.
- Using media in the classroom allows students to see concepts and new examples while watching TV, listening to music, or watching movies with friends
- Students can experience a world beyond themselves, especially when the media is completely different from the local environment. [2,77]

Language teachers often spare no effort to equip students with the necessary tools suitable for contemporary life. Since the Internet, news, and media play a vital role in our modern society, implementing media in FL classrooms is one of the main concerns of language teachers. It is unnecessary to say that teachers and education should prepare students for the real life. In this turn, media work as crucial tools to support people with information about the real world. That is way, there is no matter what sort of media is used, it can be a magazine, a newspaper, an advertisement or a short video, it is purposed at bringing a piece of real world into the classroom. Apply media into language lessons when teachers want to:

1. to introduce a real life situation,
2. to add a discovery component,
3. using authentic audio-visual channels,
4. to get students to become more involved in the lesson,
5. holding a discussion on nowadays' life, events, accidents. [3,66]

Conduct the lessons based on students' interests and hobbies.

In addition to the many advantages, teachers must also take into account some precautions when using the media. Using the media requires a thorough understanding of copyright law, some understanding of the workload involved, and some skills in identifying content, which will promote learning rather than become a distraction. The media supplements teacher-guided learning by encouraging students to listen to music, read

printed materials, or watch documentaries or movie clips. The main advantage of this method is that the teacher acts as a facilitator, helping students explain what they hear, read, or see. Students can also make media. This method uses prompting students to play the role of a teacher and creates content that attracts students and helps those master concepts. Finally, social media can also be used to enhance teaching and learning, including various online technical tools, so that people can easily communicate via the Internet to share information and resources. So, how to choose the best language teaching media from other media language teaching means. We all use it. In its simplest form, the term "teaching aids" refers to any physical material used by teachers to facilitate learning. Therefore, the media covers everything from blackboards to classroom blogs. If you grew up in the 1970s, classroom media also means motion pictures projected on an old projector. In the 1980s, it was a VHS tape. But today, the amount of media options that we can use in language teaching is simply dizzying. It seems like every new day brings another great new trend to explore. Every time we find new media, is it worth the time to add new media to our toolbox? Or sometimes the outdated media that we have always relied on may be the best? There are innovative digital media tools that can add a new dimension to our teaching. But there are some time-tested real media tools that you may not fully utilize. As we explore the vast and diverse world of language teaching media, we have already done some work for you. Here six multimedia resources to achieve a wide range of language teaching goals. The right teaching aids promote language learning. [1,11]

According to research, up to 65% of students are visual learners. This means that most of students need pictures, diagrams, videos, and diagrams to learn. Open access to real materials. Even those outdated VHS tapes allow us to access movies and TV shows in the target language that we can't find anywhere else. Students just can't get the actual linguistic contact they need from textbooks or just from you. [6] The first two media named are museum pieces today, while radio is the home of talk shows and disk jockeys, but the motion picture is still going strong, joined by television and videotapes. A well designed course of instruction can utilize these mass media to channel a student's enthusiasm and route it to an academically useful goal. Film communication offers links between classrooms and society. Motion pictures can help explore cultural context, may be integrated easily into the curriculum, are entertaining, and allow flexibility of materials and teaching techniques. Motion pictures can also be related to students' personal experiences, act as a focus for teacher student interaction, and can be used to promote awareness of the interrelationship between modes (picture, movement, language, sound, captions). TV and video are also highly valuable as teaching tools, and seen as especially effective for reaching visual learners and special populations. According to a recent wide-ranging survey, TV and video are being used more deliberately than ever before and are being more fully integrated into the curricula. Teachers look for quality programming, programs of appropriate structure and length, and advance information to allow them to preview and tape. [5,168]

To conclude, media can connect students with real audiences. If students have never really used their language skills, they will soon lose motivation to learn. Linguistic

media, like actual audio or video applications, can open up listeners to native speakers with whom they can communicate. This kind of experience makes the value of language learning more credible than simply relying on some artificial conversations that take place in the classroom. Media make content more visual.

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